

Research Article

Method Development by HPLC for Estimation of Rilpivirine in Unit Bulk and Matrix Form

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present work is to determine a novel, stability-indicating reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been developed for the quantitative determination of Rilpivirine in active pharmaceutical ingredients and in its matrix by using a symmetry BDS Hypersil C8, 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm was used with a mobile phase containing a mixture of Methanol and water (containing 0.1 % OPA) within the ratio of 80:20. The flow rate was 1.0 ml/min and effluent was monitored at 310 nm and a peak eluted at 5.50 min and column oven temperature was at room temperature. Calibration curve was plotted with a range from 5-25 μ g/ml. The developed RP-HPLC method was validated according to the current International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines for specificity, LOD, LOQ, linearity, accuracy, precision, intermediate precision, assay and robustness. The results of the study showed that the proposed RP-HPLC method is simple, rapid, precise and accurate, which is useful for the routine determination of Rilpivirine in bulk drug and in its matrix form.

INTRODUCTION

Rilpivirine chemically 4-{{4-((E)-2-cyanoethenyl)-2,6dimethylphenyl} amino}

pyrimidin-2-yl] amino} benzonitrile. Rilpivirine is a non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NNRTI) of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1). It is a diarylpyrimidine, a class of

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molecules that resemble pyrimidine nucleotides found in DNA. Because of its flexible chemical structure, resistance of rilpivirine is less likely to develop than other NNRTI's. FDA approved the Rilpivirine on May 20, 2011. Treatment of HIV-1 infections in treatment-naive patients with HIV-1 RNA $\leq 100,000$ copies/mL in combination with at least 2 other antiretroviral agents. The matrix contains 25 mg of rilpivirine, which is equivalent to 25 mg of rilpivirine. The chemical name for rilpivirine hydrochloride is 4-[[4-[[4-[(E)-2-cyanoethenyl]-2,6-dimethylphenyl]amino]2-pyrimidinyl]amino]benzonitrile monohydrochloride. Its molecular formula is $C_{22}H_{18}N_6$ [1].

Fig: 1. Structure of Rilpivirine

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Standard Drug

Rilpivirine was obtained as gift sample from Spectrum Labs India Pvt. Ltd. (Bangalore, India).

Chemicals and Reagents:

Methanol (HPLC Grade), Acetonitrile ((HPLC Grade) were obtained from Merck specialties Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai, India).

Instruments and Equipment's:

Table: 1 List of instruments used

Sr. No	Instruments Used	Model
1.	Electronic balance	Schimidzu (ModelAY-120)
2.	UV – Visible spectrophotometer	(SHIMADZU UV - 1780)
3.	HPLC system	Jasco

a.	Browin- UV software	(Version 1.5)
b.	HPLC pump	Model pu 2080 plus intelligent HPLC pump
c.	Solvent mixing module	Mx- 2080-31
d.	sample injection port	Rehodyne sample injection port with 50 loops
e.	column	Thermo scientific BDS HYPERSILTM C8 COLUMN (250mm× 4.6) (No .333s)
f.	UV - detector	MD 2010 plus single - wavelength UV detector
4.	Sonicator	Prama solution for laboratory
5.	Water purification system	Elga Lab (PURELAB UHQ-II)

Preparation of solutions:

a. Preparation of standard stock solution

Accurately weighed 10 mg Rilpivirine was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask and shaken well till it gets dissolved. After that made up the volume up to the mark of 10 ml with Methanol and mixed to make 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ stock solution (Solution A).

b. Preparation of working standard solution

1 ml of stock solution (Solution A) was diluted with methanol to get 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as a working solution (Solution B). 0.5 ml of Rilpivirine standard solution (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was pipetted into a volumetric flask and methanol was added up to 10 ml to obtain Rilpivirine solution (5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Dilutions were made up to 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ using this procedure.

Preparation of sample solution:

For this, 250 mg of matrix was weighed accurately. A quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg of Rilpivirine was weighed and

transferred to 100 mL volumetric flask containing about 60 mL of methanol and ultrasonicated for 15 min and volume was made up to the mark with the solvent. The solution was filtered through Whatman paper No. 41. One mL of this solution was transferred to 10 mL calibrated volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with the acetonitrile to get solution of concentration 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. After setting the chromatographic conditions, the matrix sample solution was injected, chromatogram was obtained, and the peak areas were recorded. The injections were repeated six times and the amount of drug present per tablet was estimated from the respective calibration curve. The % assay was found to be 99.154 ± 0.48 (mean \pm S.D.).

Mobile phase selection:

Mobile phase selection was done by various trials which was given in Table 3. In this, only one column was tried and confirmed.

Selection of Analytical wavelength:

A working solution containing Rilpivirine (5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was prepared using methanol as solvent and scanned over 200- 400 nm in UV – Spectrophotometer. It showed maximum absorbance at 310 nm. The UV Spectrum of Rilpivirine is given below.

Fig: 2 UV spectrum of Rilpivirine

Optimized chromatographic conditions:

Chromatographic conditions like column selection, mobile phase, wavelength, flow rate and run time were optimized.

Table 2 optimized chromatographic condition.

Parameter	Optimized condition
Instrument	Jasco
Detector	UV detector
Column	Thermo Scientific BDS Hypersil™ C8 (250mm×4.6mm)
Mobile phase	Methanol: Water (containing 0.1% OPA) (80: 20)
sample volume	20 μL
Type of elution	Isocratic elution
Flow rate	1 ml/min
Detection wavelength	310 nm
Run Time	10 min

Fig: 3 Representative chromatogram of Rilpivirine (5 µg/ml, RT= 5.5 minutes)

Method Validation:

The suggested analytical method was validated according to international guidelines with respect to following parameters such as precision, accuracy, linearity, robustness, ruggedness, LOD and LOQ.

System suitability:

As per the test method the standard solution were prepared and injected into HPLC from which the evaluated system suitability parameters are found to be within the limits.

Precision:

The degree of closeness of the agreement among individual test results when the method is applied to multiple samplings of a homogeneous sample. It is a measure of either the degree of reproducibility (agreement under different conditions) or repeatability (agreement under the same condition) of the method.

Accuracy:

Closeness of results was obtained by a method to the true value. It is a measure of the exactness of the method.

$$\% \text{ Bias} = \frac{\text{measure value} - \text{true value}}{\text{True value}} \times 100$$

Linearity:

The ability of the method to produce results that are directly or indirectly proportional to the concentration of the analyte in sample within a given range.

Limit of detection (LOD):

Limit of detection is the lowest concentration in a sample that can be detected, but not necessarily quantified under the stated experimental conditions.

$$\text{LOD} = 3s_a/b$$

Limit of quantification (LOQ):

Limit of quantification is the lowest concentration of analyte that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10s_a/b$$

Where, S_a - the estimate represents peaks variation.

The related calibration curve slope is given by b .

Ruggedness:

Ruggedness of an analytical method is the degree of reproducibility of test results obtained by analysis of the same samples under a variety of conditions, such as different laboratories, different analysts, different instruments, different lots of

reagents, different assay temperature and different days etc.

Robustness:

A methods robustness is defined by minor changes in parameters like the mobile phases PH, temperature, the strength of the organic solvents,

the concentration of the buffer, etc, are made but there was no recognised change in the result and are within the range as per ICH guidelines. To assess a methods robustness, experimental conditions were purposefully changed, and chromatographic characteristics were assessed.

Results and Discussion:

Table: 3 Trail run for Rilpivirine HPLC.

Column used	Observation	
<p>Column used. Thermo scientific BDS Hypersil TmC8 column (250× 4.6 mm) Mobile phase Methanol: water (containing 0.1 % Ortho phosphoric acid) (80: 20) Wavelength: 310nm</p>	<p>Sharp peak with optimum asymmetry was obtained</p>	

Method validation:

The method for Rilpivirine was validated as per the ICH guidelines ICH Q2(R1) in terms of specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantitation, and robustness.

Specificity:

Specificity was analyzed by checking different solutions like blank, standard and sample. It was then proved that there were no peaks other than drug at retention time of drug 5.08 minutes.

The method was found specific.

Fig: 4 Representative chromatogram of rilpivirine blank

Fig: 5 Representative chromatogram of Rilpivirine standard (10µg/ml).

LINEARITY:

A standard solution of Rilpivirine (100 ug/ml) was injected in the HPLC UV system of the volume 5,10,15,20 and 25 ppm, thus leading to injected amounts in the range of 5-25 ppm. This procedure was repeated for 5 times. The correlation

coefficient was found 0.9973 with equation of $y = 169912.052x + 37988$. The chromatogram was shown in the Fig. 6 for linearity. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting amount of drug injected (ppm/injection) Vs peak area shown in the. The results and details of the linearity was shown respectively.

Fig: 6 The representative chromatogram for linearity.

Fig: 7 The representative chromatogram for calibration curve.

ASSAY:

In a mortar pestle, 25 mg of Rilpivirine was geometrically mixed with 169 mg microcrystalline cellulose and 56 mg lactose as excipients to make

a synthetic mixture. From this mixture, 100 mg of blend equal to 10 mg of medication) was properly weighed and diluted to 10 ml with methanol to produce a solution (1000 µg/ml). The solution was filtered and sonicated. 6 replicates of the sample solution (10 µg/ml) were made by diluting 1 ml of the filtrate above solution to 10 ml with methanol

to get solution (10 µg/ml). Each sample solution was injected, and chromatogram was developed with mobile phase and scanned at 310 nm, with the peak area recorded. Assay of prepared blend was performed, and the % drug content was found to be 99.154% ± 0.487 (SD). The chromatogram was shown in the below fig 8

Fig: 8 Representative chromatogram for Assay.

ACCURACY:

Recovery study was carried out by performing standard addition method at 50%, 100% and 150% level. The standard drug Rilpivirine was added to pre analyzed sample solution at three levels. The basic concentration of was sample chosen was 10 µg/ml of Rilpivirine. The % mean recovery was

found to be 99.828% for Rilpivirine. At 50%, 100% and 150% levels % recovery was found to be 99.506%, 100.209% and 99.769% respectively the peak area were calculated after peak was obtained and the result are shown in the below table chromatogram was shown in the below fig 9 for Accuracy.

Fig: 9 The Representative chromatogram for Accuracy (50.100 and 150%).

Table: 4 Recovery studies

Sr. No.	Conc %	Area	Retention time	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry	Given	Obtained conc (µg/mg)
1	50%	2574084.50	7.8	2787.34	1.670	15	15
2	100%	3443326.63	7.78	2256.23	1.59	20	20
3	150%	4275974.67	7.8	2498.48	1.4650	25	25

Precision:

The precision method was done by repeatability and intermediate precision studies. In repeatability precision, injection of three-three replicates of standard solution (10, 15 & 20ug/ml) was done on the same day after some time interval. In intermediate precision, injection of six replicates of standard solution (10, 15 & 20 ug/ml three of

each) was injected in the HPLC system on two consecutive days.

The % RSD was calculated, and values were found less than 2%.

The precision result table is given in the Table. The chromatogram was shown in the Fig. 10

Fig: 10 The Representative chromatogram for precision (10ppm).

Table: 5 precision studies for Rilpivirine

A. Interday precision:

Serial no	Conc ppm	Area	RT	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry	% RSD
1	10	1736208.43	6.958	877.3	1.670	0.515
2	15	2595106.83	6.883	134.33	1.59	1.035
3	20	3434444	4.464	183.49	1.4650	0.772

B. Intraday precision:

Serial no	Conc ppm	Area	RT	Theoretical plates	Asymmetry	% RSD
1	10	1745893.50	4.689	865.66	1.822	0.293
2	15	2589958.95	4.825	1030.33	1.636	0.390
3	20	3429983.89	4.833	778.96	1.652	0.294

Amount injected	Condition	% Relative standard deviations (% RSD)
10 µg/ml	Repeatability, Intermediate	0.774, 0.326
15 µg/ml	Repeatability, Intermediate	0.774, 0.326
20 µg/ml	Repeatability, Intermediate	0.774, 0.326

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):

LOD and LOQ were calculated by y-intercept method. The LOD and LOQ were calculated using equations, $LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma/S$; $LOQ = 10 \times \sigma/S$, respectively where σ is the standard deviation of the y-intercepts and S is the slope of the calibration curve.

LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.416 and 1.261 µg/ml, respectively.

Robustness:

To evaluate the robustness of the method the chromatographic conditions were deliberately varied, and degree of reproducibility was evaluated. Robustness was carried out on standard drug solution.

Robustness of the method was carried out by changing flow rate by ± 0.5 ml/min, changing mobile phase composition by ± 2 ml and changing in wavelength by ± 1 nm. One factor at a time was varied.

The percentage RSD was found to be less than 2% which indicates that the method is robust. The robustness result is given in the Table 6

Table 6 Robustness of Rilpivirine

Parameters	Conditions	% RSD
Mobile phase composition (± 2 ml)	Methanol:	0.283
	Water (containing 0.1 % OPA) (78.22) Methanol: Water (containing 0.1% OPA) (82:18)	1.635
Flow rate (± 0.05 ml/min)	0.5 ml/min	0.189
	1.05 ml/min	0.326
Wavelength (± 1 nm)	309 nm	1.322
	311 nm	0.293

CONCLUSION:

Simple RP-HPLC method without interference from degradants has been developed and validated for the estimation of Rilpivirine as bulk drug and in tablet dosage form. This developed RP-HPLC method was validated according to ICH guidelines in terms of linearity, precision, accuracy, robust. All validation parameters were found to be within the acceptable limit in accordance with ICH guidelines. Compared with HPLC method reported 6 the established method is more sensitive

as the linearity for the method developed is in the concentration range 5-25 µg mL⁻¹ whereas for reported method, it was found to be in the concentration range 7-42 µg mL⁻¹. The developed method is simple, economic, sensitive precise, accurate, and reproducible. The developed method can be used for quantitative analysis of drug in pharmaceutical dosage form.

REFERENCES

1. S. M. Khopkar, (1997) Basic concepts of analytical chemistry. 2nd ed. New age International Ltd. Publishers: 1, New Delhi, 1998, 178-179.
2. Sharma, B. K. (2000) Instrumental methods of chemical analysis. Krishna Prakashan Media
3. Beckett, Arnold Heyworth, and John Bedford Stenlake, (1988) eds. Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry: Part II 4th Ed. Vol. 2. A&C Black.
4. Christian, Gary D. (1994) "Analytical chemistry." John Wiley & Sons, USA: 331
5. Beckett A. H, Stenlake J. B, Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry, 4th Ed., New Delhi: CBS Publishers and Distributors Pvt. Ltd, 2007, 255-295.
6. A.V. Kasture, S.G. Wadodkar, K.R. Mahadik, H.M. More, Pharmaceutical analysis, Vol. I, 17th Edn, 2007, 1-3.
7. <https://www.osti.gov/Spectroscopy.pdf>
8. Egon Stahl, Thin- Layer Chromatography A Laboratory Handbook 2nd edition, Springer 2006, 52-66.
9. H.H. Willard, L.L. Merritt, J.A. Dean, F.A. Settle, Instrumental methods of analysis. 7th Edn, CBS publishers and distributors, New Delhi, 2001, 614- 629.
10. G. R. Chatwal, S. K. Anand, Instrumental Methods of Chemical Analysis, 5th Ed., Himalaya Publishing House, Delhi, 2004, 1.6-1.7, 2.156-2.158

11. P. D. Sethi, (2001) High Performance Liquid Chromatography in Quantitative Analysis of Pharmaceutical Formulations, 1st Ed, CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 3-11 and 116-120.
12. Ashutosh Khar, Pharmaceutical Analysis vol II, Page no.-299-305.
13. R. MeYer Veronica, (1993) Practical High Performance Liquid Chromatography nd Edn, John Wiley and sons, London 246-258.
14. Muhammad Sajid, Kunal Rehman. Essentials of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Spinger (e- book) ,2020. n
15. ICH. Q1A. (R2): stability testing of new drug substances and products, International Conference on Harmonization, Geneva. 2003.
16. ICH. Q1 (B). Harmonized Tripartite Guideline, Stability testing: Photostability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products. In: Proceeding of the International Conference on Harmonization, Geneva. 1996.
17. ICH. Q3B: guideline on impurities in new drug product, international conference on Harmonization. Geneva; 2005.
18. FDA. Draft Guidance for industry on Analytical Procedures and Methods Validation Chemistry, Manufacturing, and control documentation Federal Register. 2000; 65(169):52776-52777.
19. Carstensen J, Rhodes C. Drug stability, principles and practices. New York: Marcel Dekker; 2005.
20. Bakshi M, Singh S. Development of validated stability-indicating assay methods-critical review. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2002; 28(6):1011-1040. Doi: 10.1016/s07317085(02)00047-x, PMID 12049968. Blessy M, Patel Ruchi D, Prajapat.
21. Brummer H. How to approach a forced degradation study life sciences Technology [bulletin]. Vol. 31; 2011. p. 1-4.
22. ICH Q2(R1), validation of analytical procedures, text and methodology; 2005.
23. FDA. Draft guidance for industry on analytical procedures and methods validation chemistry, manufacturing and control documentation. Fed Regist. 2014; 65(169):52776- 52777.
24. Nash RA, Wachter AH. Validation of analytical methods process. In: Pharmaceutical process validation. 3rd Ed. New York: Marcel Dekker Inc; 2003. p. 507-524

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